

Equilibrium Studies on the Formation of Mixed-Ligand Complexes in Solution—Part II

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pH-metric investigations have been carried out on the formation of the ternary complex MAB [M=copper(II), nickel(II) or zinc(II) ion, A=iminodiacetate and B=serinate, β -alaninate or malonate]. The overall formation constants of the complexes have been evaluated at 30° and ionic strength of 0.2M (NaNO₃). The order of stabilities of the complexes is found to be in keeping with the Irving-Williams order. The values of the stability constants are compared and discussed in terms of basicity, size of the chelate ring, charge neutralisation and statistical considerations.

TERNARY complex formation has received widespread interest in the past two decades because of the involvement of mixed chelation in many biological processes¹. In a variety of analytical methods based on complex formation—separations involving liquid-liquid extractions, titrimetry and gravimetric analysis—ternary chelates are involved². Statistical considerations also indicate favoured formation of ternary complexes³. Ternary complexes of various metal ions involving diamines, amino acids and carboxylic acids as ligands have been extensively studied^{4,5}. Complexes of metal ions with iminodiacetic acid as primary ligand and some amino acids and diamines as secondary ligands have also been studied by many workers⁶⁻⁸. Results of investigations on the formation of mixed chelates by copper(II), nickel(II) and zinc(II) with iminodiacetic acid (imda) as primary ligand and L-serine, β -alanine and malonic acid as secondary ligands are reported here.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of AR grade. The solutions were prepared from double distilled water. The metal solutions, prepared from their respective nitrates, were estimated by standard procedures. Malonic acid solution was standardised using potassium hydroxide.

The titrations were carried out under an atmosphere of nitrogen in a thermostated bath at 30±0.1°. The ionic strength of the solution was maintained at 0.2M using sodium nitrate. Measurements of *pH* were made as described in an earlier paper⁹. The *pH* value was converted into hydrogen ion concentration by using a hydrogen ion activity coefficient of 0.81°.

Results and Discussion

The acid dissociation constants of the ligands under the present experimental conditions were

redetermined by the method of Albert and Serjeant¹¹. The Calvin and Wilson titration technique¹² was adopted for the study of the formation of binary complexes and the stability constants were evaluated following the method of Irving and Rossotti¹³. The values of the acid dissociation constants of the ligands and the formation constants of the binary complexes are given in Table 1 and

TABLE 1—IONISATION CONSTANTS OF THE LIGANDS AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF BINARY COMPLEXES
[Temp. = 30±0.1°, μ = 0.2M (NaNO₃)]

Ligand	pK_1	pK_2			
imda	2.61±0.01	9.16±0.03			
serine	2.25±0.01	8.95±0.02			
β -alanine	3.60±0.01	10.16±0.04			
malonic acid	2.68±0.02	5.22±0.02			
Ligand		Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Zn(II)	
imda	log K_1	10.51±0.08	8.18±0.06	6.98±0.04	
	log K_2	5.60±0.05	6.22±0.06	6.14±0.07	
L-serine	log K_1	7.84±0.02	5.40±0.03	4.68±0.04	
	log K_2	6.47±0.06	4.28±0.04	3.71±0.05	
β -alanine	log K_1	7.04±0.02	4.64±0.03	—	
	log K_2	5.54±0.04	3.93±0.05	—	
malonic acid	log K_1	4.97±0.04	3.17±0.05	2.69±0.03	
	log K_2	2.78±0.06	—	—	

are in good agreement with the literature values¹⁴. The variation of *pH* with number of moles of base added (per mole of metal ion) in the titrations for studying the formation of complexes is shown in Fig. 1. Curve 1 represents the Cu(II)-imda titration in 1 : 1 molar ratio. Curve 2 is the titration of cupric ions in the presence of both imda and malonic acid in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio. The buffer region representing complex formation occurs in this curve at a relatively lower *pH* compared to curve 1 and consequently the simultaneous formation of simple and mixed chelates may be inferred. Curve 3 represents Cu(II)-imda-serine titration in 1 : 1 : 1 molar ratio. Eventhough this curve closely follows curve 1, indicating that Cu(iminodiacetate) species

Fig. 1. Cu^{2+} -imda-secondary ligand system
 1. $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2(0.008M) + \text{imda}(0.008M)$
 2. $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2(0.008M) + \text{imda}(0.008M)$
 + malonic acid (0.008M)
 3. $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2(0.008M) + \text{imda}(0.008M) + \text{serine}(0.008M)$
 'a' refers to the number of moles of base added per mole of metal ion.

predominates in the initial stages of the titration, there is an apparent overlap of the buffer regions in which the simple and ternary complexes are formed. Thus the formation of mixed chelate commences before the completion of the formation of the primary complex and the results of the calculations are in keeping with such an inference. Also it is observed that there is an appreciable dissociation of the primary complex in the buffer region where the ternary complex is formed, resulting in the formation of species like $\text{Cu}(\text{iminodiacetate})_2$, $\text{Cu}(\text{serinate})$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{serinate})_2$, in addition to the mixed chelate. The nature of the titration curves for the metal ions $\text{Ni}(\text{II})$ and $\text{Zn}(\text{II})$ are similar to that of the above mentioned curves. The following mass balance equations were used to evaluate the stability constant of the mixed chelate. $\text{H}_2\text{A} = \text{imda}$, $\text{H}_2\text{B} = \text{secondary ligand}$ (charges have been omitted for convenience).

$$M_T = [M] + [MA] + [MA_2] + [MB] + [MB_2] + [MAB] \\
A_T = [H_2A] + [HA] + [A] + [MA] + 2[MA_2] + [MAB] \\
B_T = [H_2B] + [HB] + [B] + [MB] + 2[MB_2] + [MAB] \text{ and } H_T - C_B = [H] - [\text{OH}] + 2[H_2A] + [HA] + 2[H_2B] + [HB]$$

M_T , A_T , B_T and H_T represent the total concentrations of metal ion, primary ligand, secondary ligand and hydrogen ion respectively. C_B is the concentration of the added base. In the region where the calculations were performed, the hydroxo species would be present only in negligible amounts, and it was also ascertained that species like MB_2 or MB_2A was not present in appreciable concentrations under the experimental conditions. Calculations using the above equations were similar to those of Martin and Paris¹⁰. A computer programme was used to evaluate the formation constant of the ternary complex and the concentrations of the various species present in the solution. The values of the stability constants are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—M(II)-IMDA-SECONDARY LIGAND SYSTEM
 STABILITY CONSTANTS OF TERNARY COMPLEXES*

(Temp. = $30 \pm 0.1^\circ$; $\mu = 0.2M$ (NaNO_3))

$$\beta_{MAB} = \frac{[MAB]}{[M][A][B]}; K_{MAB} = \frac{[MAB]}{[MA][B]}; K_{MB} = \frac{[MB]}{[M][B]}$$

$$\Delta \log K = \log K_{MAB} - \log K_{MB}$$

Secondary ligand		Cu(II)	Ni(II)	Zn(II)
glycine [@]	$\log \beta_{MAB}$	18.20	12.95	10.97
	$\log K_{MAB}$	5.60	4.77	3.99
	$\Delta \log K$	-2.50	-1.09	-1.08
β -alanine	$\log \beta_{MAB}$	16.42	11.85	—
	$\log K_{MAB}$	4.91	3.67	—
	$\Delta \log K$	-2.13	-0.95	—
L-serine	$\log \beta_{MAB}$	15.86	12.58	10.56
	$\log K_{MAB}$	5.35	4.40	3.58
	$\Delta \log K$	-2.49	-1.00	-1.10
malonic acid	$\log \beta_{MAB}$	12.78	10.20	8.94 [£]
	$\log K_{MAB}$	2.92	2.02	1.98 [£]
	$\Delta \log K$	-2.75	-1.15	-0.79
en [@]	$\log \beta_{MAB}$	18.65	14.76	12.17
	$\log K_{MAB}$	8.14	6.58	5.19
	$\Delta \log K$	-2.98	-0.82	-0.79

* The general accuracy of the results is ± 0.1 log unit.

[@] V.V. Ramanujam and V.M. Selvarajan, unpublished results

[£] Literature value—reference 20.

It is seen from Table 2 that for all the secondary ligands investigated, the β_{MAB} values as well as the K_{MAB} values follow the order of stabilities $\text{Cu}(\text{II}) > \text{Ni}(\text{II}) > \text{Zn}(\text{II})$, which is in keeping with the Irving-Williams order¹⁰. In order to have meaningful comparison of the results, the β_{MAB} values for M(II)-imda-glycine (or) ethylenediamine(en) obtained by the present authors by the methods of calculations mentioned earlier, are also given in Table 2. The β_{MAB} values for M(II)-imda-serine system are less than the corresponding values for M(II)-imda-glycine system. The smaller value for serinate complex relative to that of glycinate complex is due to the lower basicity of the amino group in serine. The β_{MAB} values for M(II)-imda- β -alanine system are less

than the corresponding values of M(II)-imda-glycine (or) serine system, even though the basicity of the amino group in β -alanine is much higher. This is due to the greater strain involved in the formation of a six-membered ring by β -alanine, compared to the more favoured five-membered ring formed by glycine or serine.

The favoured formation of ternary complex can be inferred from the values of $\Delta \log K$, the difference between the stability constants ($\log K_{MAB} - \log K_{MB}$). Sigel¹⁷ has shown that when both the primary and secondary ligands are bidentate, the statistical value of $\Delta \log K$ is -0.40 . It can be shown⁸ that when one of the ligands is terdentate, the statistical value of $\Delta \log K$ is -0.70 . The $\Delta \log K$ values in Table 2 indicate that for Ni(II) and Zn(II) the values are nearer to the statistical value. There is a deviation from the statistical value in the case of Cu(II). In the mixed chelate of Cu(II) three chelate rings are involved, and it is well-known that the addition of a third chelate ring to a bis-chelate of copper(II) is always difficult. For instance, the $\log K_3$ value for the addition of ethylenediamine(en) to $Cu(en)_2$ has been shown to be negative¹⁸. The formation of a third chelate ring in Cu(II) necessitates bonding in the apical position and the Jahn-Teller effects operating in Cu(II) complexes of higher coordination number renders this difficult.

The general trend of the $\Delta \log K$ values indicate that mixed-ligand complexation is more favoured with en than with α -amino acids which form 5-membered chelate rings as en. This may be due to the effect of charge neutralisation which is one of the major factors favouring ternary complexes. The neutralisation of charges when the mixed-ligand complex is formed from the parent complexes can be represented as below :

The favoured formation of ternary complex due to charge neutralisation has been observed in many cases. Sigel and his coworkers¹⁹ have observed that Cu(bipyridyl) (oxalate) is favoured to Cu(bipyridyl)(en) as a result of charge neutralisation. The distribution of various complex species present in a system as a function of pH gives an idea of the favoured formation of ternary complexes. The distribution curves for representative species are given for Cu(II)-imda-serine system in Fig. 2. It is seen that around pH 5, about 90% of total metal ion is present as Cu(iminodiacetate) and 5% of Cu(serinate) is also formed. As the pH increases the concentration of Cu(iminodiacetate) gradually decreases and reaches about 20% at pH 7.5. At the same time the concentration of the ternary complex gradually increases with pH and reaches 50% at pH 7.5. $Cu(\text{serinate})_2$ and $Cu(\text{iminodiacetate})_2$ are also formed as the pH increases, and their concentration reaches

Fig. 2. Cu^{++} -iminodiacetate(A)-serinate(B) system

Distribution of complexes

1. CuA 2. CuA_2 3. CuB 4. CuB_2 5. $CuAB$

around 15% each at pH 7.5. The distribution of complexes for Ni(II) or Zn(II)-imda-serine system is similar to the earlier system. With malonic acid as secondary ligand, the concentration of the ternary complex formed is found to be much less. The maximum concentration of the mixed complex is only 12% under the experimental conditions for Cu(II). In the case of Ni(II) and Zn(II) the concentration of malonic acid has to be increased to 0.004 M for an appreciable amount of ternary complex to be formed; the maximum concentrations of the mixed chelate are found to be 10% and 7% of the total metal ion for Ni(II) and Zn(II) respectively when malonic acid is the secondary ligand.

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